

A novel coumarinyl scaffold as metal ion sensor towards spectrophotometric detection of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ion

Pranabes Bhattacharyya, Arunima Medda, Dinesh C. Gorain, Bijon Kr. Pal, Nikhil Guchhait and Asish R. Das*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : archem@caluniv.ac.in, ardas66@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 13 September 2011, accepted 16 December 2011

Abstract : A new series of coumarin based metal ion sensors have been prepared devising a green protocol involving ethyl-(L)-lactate as a polar solvent. These compounds either selectively bind with specific transitional metal ions or form complexes with specific photophysical character when subjected to absorption spectroscopy. The derived Schiff's bases quantitatively bind with metal ions to form 1 : 1 complexes making them a useful tool for qualitative estimation of metal ions in biological as well as organic systems.

Keywords : Coumarin, Schiff's base, metal ion sensor.

Introduction

Systems containing coumarinyl scaffold are of immense importance in studying and engineering biological systems¹⁻⁶. Many coumarinyl compounds have been utilized in generating a library of compounds with various biological activities. Moreover coumarin systems containing a lactone ring embedded within has been studied in details for the characteristic properties in absorption and emission spectroscopy⁷⁻¹⁵. Coumarin rings are also being extensively used in synthesis of fluorescent dyes and pigments⁷⁻⁹.

Schiff's bases are generally used as metal ion sensors as they possess very firm affinity towards metal ions, more specifically transition metal ions and as a consequence form stable metal ion complexes with typical photophysical properties which make them a useful tool for qualitative as well as quantitative metal ion estimation.

In the recent era of chemistry, determination of transition metal compounds is considered necessary because of the increasing interest in bioinorganic and organic catalytic chemistry, increased industrial use, and also their enhanced discharge, toxic properties, and other adverse effects. On the one hand, transition-metal ions such as Cu^{2+} ions are essential in the human body and participate in enzymatic catalysis and gene expression¹⁶⁻¹⁹. On the other hand, a high level of transition-metal ions could

be toxic to biological systems. For instance, high concentrations of Ni^{2+} ions may cause a reduction in plant growth by reducing concentrations of chlorophyll a and b, cytochrome b6 and b559, and ferredoxin^{20,21}. Their determination is nowadays considered necessary. The available methods for low-level estimation of transition metal ions in solution include spectroscopy, mass spectrometry (MS), inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES), and also inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Other methods include isotopic dilution mass spectrometry, neutron activation analysis, X-ray fluorescence spectrometry etc. These methods are either time-consuming, involving multiple sample manipulations or too expensive for most analytical laboratories.

Although coumarinyl systems have been studied for many photophysical and biological properties, but the metal ion sensing capabilities of coumarinyl Schiff's bases have not been explored in extent. Hence we planned to synthesize a series of coumarinyl Schiff's bases employing a green protocol using ethyl-(L)-lactate as the most suitable solvent²² with an *ortho* hydroxyl group to the aldehyde moiety anticipating greater chelating ability with transition metal ions. Accordingly, we also tried to understand their complexation ability with transition metal ions (viz. Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) in CH_3CN solvent by using absorption spectroscopy and emission spectroscopy as well.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

In our study, we chose three coumarin based amines **A**, **B**, **C** and coupled them with two aldehydes **D** and **E** to obtain five different coumarinyl Schiff's bases (Table 1)

Table 1. Synthesis of coumarinyl Schiff's base

Entry	Amine	Aldehyde	Product	Yield (%)	Time (min)
1	A	D		84	30
2	B	D		89	20
3	C	D		78	55
4	A	E		71	20
5	B	E		91	15

which were further studied for their photophysical properties and metal binding capacities.

Absorption spectra :

Structurally the synthetic molecules have ligand binding sites and may be suitable for binding with metal ions with the formation of complexes. The formation and stability of such complexes depend on the nature of binding between the two partners, the suitable architecture of the ligand unit at the binding condition and proper selection of the metal ions. In all cases the molecules having aromatic unit are capable for $\pi\pi^*$ type of expected absorption spectra. Binding with metals ions with the formation of stable complexes can modify the $\pi\pi^*$ transition and hence this transition can be used as suitable probe for metal ion sensors. A quantitative evaluation of the strength of the interaction of the ligands with the metal ions can be estimated from the Benesi-Hildebrand equation in terms of determination of the binding constant (K) and the Gibbs free energy for the interaction^{23,24}. In this section, we present a brief overview of the Benesi-Hildebrand equation which has been quite extensively used for quantitative estimation of a binding or complexation equilibrium phenomenon since years. The binding or complexation equilibrium between the ligand and the metal ions can be expressed as :

$$K = \frac{[L : M^{n+}]}{[L][M^{n+}]} \quad (2)$$

where K is the binding constant and the terms within square brackets represent the concentrations of respective species.

Benesi-Hildebrand relation for these types of complexation reactions is expressed as (1) :

$$K = \frac{[L : M^{n+}]}{([L]_0 - [L : M^{n+}])([M^{n+}] - [L : M^{n+}])} \quad (3)$$

According to literature reports²⁴⁻²⁷, under the consideration $[M^{n+}] \gg [L : M^{n+}]$, eq. (3) can be written as :

$$K = \frac{[L : M^{n+}]}{([L]_0 - [L : M^{n+}])([M^{n+}])} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{[L : M^{n+}]}{[L]_0} = \frac{A_0 - A}{A_0 - A_1} \quad (5)$$

Now, A_0 , A and A_1 are the absorbances, respectively in the absence of, at intermediate and infinite concentration of metal ion, so that.

After combining eqs. (4) and (5) and then rearranging the same, following expression is obtained²⁴⁻²⁷

$$\frac{1}{(A - A_0)} = \frac{1}{(A_1 - A_0)} + \frac{1}{(A_1 - A_0)K[M^{n+}]} \quad (6)$$

A plot of $1/(A - A_0)$ vs $1/[M^{n+}]$ will allow the determination of stoichiometry as well as the binding constant (K) for the complexation process. If the plot complies with linear regression it will confirm a 1 : 1 stoichiometry and the binding constant will be given by $K = \text{intercept to slope ratio}$.

The absorption spectra of the ligand **1** in the presence of different metal ions are presented in Fig. 1. As can be seen in the figure the absorption profile of the ligand **1** undergo noticeable modification in the presence of the studied metal ions whereby forming a platform for prospective use of **1** as a probable sensor for the metal ions. In order to elaborate on the issue the absorption spectra of **1** have been taken in the presence of a series of concentrations of the studied metal ions and the results are displayed in the figure (Fig. 1). The inset of the figure shows the Benesi-Hildebrand plot for $1-M^{n+}$ interaction

given in Table 2. Table 2 also reflects a negative change of free energy for the $1-M^{n+}$ complexation process and thereby indicating the spontaneity of the process. Table 2 and Fig. 1 also highlight the fact that the absorption spectral changes of the ligand **1** in the presence of different metal ions do not follow the same pattern. This is not surprising and can be connected to the differential coordinating ability of the ligand towards different metal ions and the differential stability of the resultant complex²⁸.

Similarly the ligand **3** promises to be a viable candidate for the development of chemo sensor for Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions based on its absorption spectral modification induced by the presence of the metal ions, as given in Fig. 2. Here also, the spectral modifications of the ligand **3** in the presence of various metal ions are not found to follow a common pattern. Moreover, the isobestic points observed at 393 nm for $3-Zn^{2+}$ and at 407 nm for $3-Ni^{2+}$ probably indicate the equilibrium between the free ligand and the complex. Such an observation was not noted with the ligand **1**, which can again be connected to an indication of the differential coordinating abilities of different ligands towards the metal ions and/or differential stabilities of the resultant complexes.

Emission spectra :

The synthesized molecules were expected to be fluorescent as they contain a coumarin ring and that also in

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of ligand **1** in the presence of increasing concentration of (a) Ni^{2+} ion and (b) Cu^{2+} ion. Direction of arrow indicates increasing concentration of the metal ion. Insets show the respective Benesi-Hildebrand plots.

in respective cases. According to the above discussion the linear regression of the Benesi-Hildebrand plot in each case indicates the formation of a 1 : 1 stoichiometry for the $1-M^{n+}$ complex. The strength of binding interaction can be rationalized from the binding constant values as

conjugation with electron rich aromatic moiety. They show significant change in their absorption spectra in presence of certain divalent transition metal cation, observing that the change in the emission spectra of the ligands in presence of those metal ions were also measured.

Table 2. Binding constant (K), free energy change (ΔG) and absorption maxima ($\lambda_{\text{abs}}^{\text{max}}$) for complexation reaction

Metal	Ligand	K (M^{-1})	ΔG (kJ/mol) at 298 K	$\lambda_{\text{abs}}^{\text{max}}$ (nm)
Cu^{2+}	1	4140.16	-20.63	460
Ni^{2+}		2462.79	-19.35	480
Zn^{2+}		6450.55	-21.73	455
Ni^{2+}	4	20637.89	-24.61	490
Zn^{2+}		5956.55	-21.53	465
Ni^{2+}	3	76310.44	-27.85	495
Zn^{2+}		57642.93	-27.16	475

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of ligand 3 in the presence of increasing concentration of (a) Ni^{2+} ion and (b) Zn^{2+} ion. Direction of arrow indicates increasing concentration of the metal ions. Insets show the respective Benesi-Hildebrand plots.

For the emission spectroscopic study the ligands were excited at the wave length where these ligands showed absorption peak in absorption spectra. The ligand 1 showed significant enhancement of emission in presence of Cu^{2+} ion. This dramatic increase in the fluorescence intensity is most probably due to coordination of the Cu^{2+} ion to the fluorophore. Addition of 1 eqv. of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ in the acetonitrile solution of 1 and excitation at 350 nm (the absorption maxima of pure ligand) led to a 4.5 fold enhancement of the emission at 409 nm (Fig. 3).

Along with Cu^{2+} , the synthesized molecule 1 is also capable of sensing Zn^{2+} cation in a very dilute concentration as shown in Fig. 4.

The preference of Cu^{2+} suggests that large ionic radius of Cu^{2+} has a complementary size to the pseudo cavity formed by the ligand for encapsulation in the binding sites. Thus it can be seen as an example of better binding of Cu^{2+} with a receptor according to its size rather than its acidity.

The change of fluorescence emission was also moni-

tored for the ligand 2 in presence of Cu^{2+} in varying concentration. But here on increasing the metal ion concentration, a sharp quenching of the fluorescence is observed (Fig. 5). This sharp quenching of fluorescence is attributed to the formation of complex between the ligand and metal ion. But the difference in the pattern of change in fluorescence of ligand 1 and 2 are different. In case of ligand 1, the lactone fluorophore is incorporated in the metal binding site where as in ligand 2 the metal ion binding site has no electronic influence from the lactone fluorophore.

Fig. 3. Emission enhancement of ligand 1 in presence of Cu^{2+} ion ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 350$ nm).

The quenching of the fluorescence is more prominent in case of ligand 5 which is most probably due to the additional fluorophore azo group attached to the ligand which though does not participate directly in the com-

Fig. 4. Emission enhancement of ligand 1 in presence of Zn^{2+} ion ($\lambda_{ex} = 350$ nm).

Fig. 6. Emission quenching of ligand 5 in presence of Cu^{2+} ion ($\lambda_{ex} = 275$ nm).

Fig. 5. Emission quenching of ligand 2 in presence of Cu^{2+} ion ($\lambda_{ex} = 275$ nm).

plexation with the metal ion but enhances the coordinating ability of the ligand with Cu^{2+} ion (Fig. 6).

After observing the capability of the ligands to show significant change in the fluorescence property in presence of even a very low concentration of a specific metal ion we tried to explore the possibility of these ligands to be used as a probe to detect the presence of certain transition metal ions in presence of other metal ions. To observe the sensitivity of the ligand 5 in sensing Cu^{2+} ion selectively in presence of Ni^{2+} , we checked the response of the ligand 5 in a binary mixtures of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} in

different ratios and found that in presence of Ni^{2+} there is no change of spectral pattern observed with increasing concentration of Cu^{2+} ion (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Detection of Cu^{2+} using ligand 5 in presence of Ni^{2+} .

Conclusion :

In summary, we can conclude that we have succeeded in developing a series of coumarin based Schiff's base compounds which can be a probe in the detection of specific transition metal ions and can also be used for selective detection of a metal ion in presence of another. We are further hopeful about the application of these compounds in detection and removal of metal ions from physiological system.

Experimental

General procedure :

For synthesis of all the Schiff's bases 1 mmol each of the amine and the aldehyde were dissolved in 2 ml ethyl-(L)-lactate and heated gently at 60° for desired time (as mentioned in Table 1) and then poured into cold water. The crude product was then filtered, washed with brine and finally crystallized from ethanol to obtain pure Schiff's bases (1-5).

3-[(2-Hydroxy-benzylidene)-amino]-chromen-2-one : Schiff's base 1 was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 2-hydroxy-benzaldehyde and 3-amino coumarin and was isolated as an orange solid. m.p. 188 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3424 (O-H), 1722 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1453; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) : δ 10.78 (1H, s), 10.18 (1H, s), 7.61 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8 Hz and 1.5 Hz), 7.44-7.47 (1H, m), 7.32-7.35 (1H, m), 7.15-7.21 (3H, m), 6.91-6.95 (2H, m), 6.69 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) : δ 160.9, 159.1, 148.2, 136.8, 133.5, 129.9, 125.8, 125.1, 124.9, 122.5, 122.0, 119.9, 117.5, 115.7, 108.3; [M+H] for C₁₆H₁₁NO₃; Calcd. : 266.0818, Found : 266.0811.

6-[(2-Hydroxy-benzylidene)-amino]-chromen-2-one : Schiff's base 2 was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 2-hydroxy-benzaldehyde and 6-amino coumarin and was isolated as an orange solid. m.p. 154 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3435 (O-H), 2373, 1722 (C=O), 1619 (C=N), 1562; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 8.65 (1H, s), 7.73 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz), 7.38-7.65 (6H, m), 6.85-7.13 (2H, m), 6.48 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 163.4, 161.1, 152.7, 145.1, 142.9, 133.7, 132.5, 124.6, 119.9, 119.4, 119.3, 118.9, 118.0, 117.6, 117.4; [M+H] for C₁₆H₁₁NO₃ Calcd. : 266.0818, Found : 266.0823.

3-[(2-Hydroxy-benzylidene)-amino]-benzo[h]chromen-2-one : Schiff's base 3 was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 2-hydroxy-benzaldehyde and 3-amino benzocoumarin and was isolated as an orange solid. m.p. 214 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3449 (O-H), 3338, 1714 (C=O), 1677 (C=N), 1598, 1377; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) : δ 10.73 (1H, s), 10.25 (1H, s), 8.30 (2H, m), 8.22 (1H, d, *J* 4.2 Hz), 7.97 (1H, d, *J* 4.2 Hz), 7.79 (1H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz), 7.40-7.66 (3H, m), 6.94-6.99 (3H, m); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) : δ 160.7, 158.5, 145.6, 136.5,

133.4, 129.5, 129.26, 128.7, 127.6, 127, 126.9, 125.9, 125.6, 122.2, 121.4, 119.5, 119.2, 117.3, 116.6, 116.4, 115.9; [M+H] for C₂₀H₁₃NO₃; Calcd. : 316.0974, Found : 316.2170.

3-[(2-Hydroxy-5-phenylazo-benzylidene)-amino]-chromen-2-one : Schiff's base 4 was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 2-hydroxy-4-azophenyl-benzaldehyde and 3-amino coumarin and was isolated as an orange solid. m.p. 162 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3423 (O-H), 3035, 1713 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1482; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) : δ 11.48 (1H, s), 10.33 (1H, s), 8.04-8.15 (2H, m), 7.81-7.84 (2H, m), 7.49-7.57 (3H, m), 7.35-7.38 (1H, m), 7.15-7.23 (4H, m), 6.67 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) : δ 163.3, 131.2, 129.8, 129.5, 125.4, 124.8, 124.5, 123.9, 122.7, 122.4, 121.8, 118.5, 117.7, 115.5, 107.8; [M+H] for C₂₂H₁₅N₃O₃; Calcd. : 370.1192, Found : 370.1188.

6-[(2-Hydroxy-5-phenylazo-benzylidene)-amino]-chromen-2-one : Schiff's base 5 was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 2-hydroxy-4-azophenyl-benzaldehyde and 6-amino coumarin and was isolated as an orange solid. m.p. 146 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3439 (O-H), 3054, 1739 (C=O), 1619 (C=N), 1564; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 8.78 (1H, s), 8.06 (2H, m), 7.89 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 7.75 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 7.40-7.52 (6H, m), 7.16 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 6.5 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 163.7, 162.9, 160.2, 152.9, 152.6, 145.8, 144.5, 142.8, 130.7, 129.1, 127.9, 124.6, 122.6, 120.0, 119.5, 118.2, 118.1, 117.1; [M+H] for C₂₂H₁₅N₃O₃; Calcd. : 370.1192, Found : 370.1192.

Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge the financial support from UGC and Calcutta University. PB thanks CSIR for the Senior Research Fellowship.

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